

Evaluation of Soils and Climatic Conditions Supporting Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) Production in College of Agronomy Research Farms of Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Makurdi is in a strategic position in the agricultural map of Nigeria, producing a wide range of both annual and perennial crops such as yam, maize, rice, sorghum, soybean, cowpea, citrus, mangoes, and a variety of vegetables. One of the factors responsible for this wide range of crops is the favorable climate. This study was aimed at evaluating the suitability of the soils for the production of groundnut and to have a detailed soil database for effective land use planning. Soil requirements for groundnut were obtained from past research works and compared with data collected from the survey. The study showed that the soils of the area had formed under climatic environment presently characterized by an annual rainfall of about 1330.20 mm and a mean annual temperature of about 27.80 °C. The soils were well drained to poorly drained. The clay content ranged from 7.20 to 29.30 %, increasing with depth. Organic carbon was low (0.64 %) in the upland, but relatively high when compared with the low (0.62 %) value in the low land. The suitability assessment results showed that although, certain quantities or characteristics such as mean annual temperature, relative humidity and base saturation were optimum for groundnut cultivation, there was however, no highly suitable (S_1) land for groundnut cultivation in the area. All the soils were classified into moderately suitable (S_{2f}) subclass due to their low nutrient levels. COATRF I and II units of the area were moderately suitable (S_{2f}) due to topography and low soil fertility. COATRF III was limited by its imperfect drainage to marginally suitable subclass (S_{3wf}) for groundnut production. To improve on the level of productivity of the soils for optimal groundnut production, management techniques such as continuous organic matter incorporation and mineral fertilizer application, and efficient use of mineral fertilizers with low levels of chemical inputs with adaption of appropriate irrigation techniques would make dry season farming sustainable.

Key words: evaluation, groundnut, climatic conditions, Makurdi, soils.

Introduction

The broad principles of land evaluation involve comparing the requirements of land use with quality of land thereby assessing the value of each type of land present for each land use (Dent, 1981). Decisions on land use are being based on comprehensive analysis of the production and potentials of natural resources such as climate, soil and hydrology (Abagyeh, 2016). Soil evaluation is very important in this direction as it provides information on the potentials and constraints of land for a defined land use type in terms of crop performance as affected by the physical environment. Soil evaluations are based on knowledge of crop requirements, prevailing conditions and applied soil management methods (Ande, 2011). Soil evaluation for suitability classification quantifies in broad terms to what extent soil conditions match crop requirements under a defined input and management (FAO, 1976). Evaluating the soil enables optimum performance and maximum productivity of the crop. In evaluation, the specific crop requirements will be calibrated with the terrain and soil parameters (Dent, 1981), so that the identified limiting factors could be managed to suit crop requirements and improve productivity. Land evaluation thus, enables management guidelines in order to promote a more sustainable use of the soil and environmental resources (Maniyunda, 2007).

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is a member of sub-family, papilionaceae of the family Leguminosae. It is believed to be the native of Brazil to Peru, Argentina and China. It was introduced into India during the first half of the sixteenth century from one of the pacific islands of China. Groundnut oil is an edible oil. It finds extensive use as a cooking medium both as refined oil and Vanaspati Ghee. "They are rich in protein and vitamins A, B and some members of B2 group. Nigeria is the largest groundnut producing country in West Africa, accounting for 51 % of production in the region. The country contributes 10 % of total global production and 39 % that of Africa. Between 1956 and 1967, groundnut was the country's most valuable single export crop, exemplified by the famous Kano groundnut pyramids. Groundnut is a major source of edible oil as well as livelihoods for small-scale farmers in Northern Nigeria. Being a labor-intensive crop, it generates employment for the rural poor. It is planted on about 34 % of total cultivated area and contributes to 23 % of household cash revenue. Groundnut products like oil and cake accounted for a significant percentage of total Nigerian export earnings. Before the fossil oil boom, groundnut was one of the major sources of revenue and foreign exchange earnings. However, in the post-1967 period, the combined effects of drought, increasing prevalence of diseases such as rust, leaf spots and groundnut rosette disease (GRD) have caused a decline in groundnut production. The total output of groundnut in 1970 was 1.6 m tons, but fell to 0.47 m tons in 1980. Due to insufficient groundnut stocks, processors and marketers in Kano State source groundnut from as far as Chad Republic.

The year-round demand for groundnut means farmers can increase production without any fear of market glut. Since 1984, production has been increasing at an estimated growth rate of 8 %, resulting both from area expansion (6 %), and increase in productivity of 2 % (Ndjeunga et al., 2010). Hence, the study was to evaluate the soils and climatic conditions

supporting groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) production in College of Agronomy Research Farm of University of Agriculture Makurdi Benue State

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted within the teaching and research farm of the College of Agronomy University of Agriculture, Makurdi. The University lies North-east of Makurdi town which is between Latitude 7.45° N and 7.50° N and Longitude of 8.00° E and 9.00° E. Makurdi is in a strategic position in the Agricultural map of Nigeria, producing a wide range of both annual and perennial crops such as groundnut, sorghum, soybean, cowpea, rice, maize, yam, citrus, mangoes and a variety of vegetables; one of the factors responsible for this wide range of crops is the favorable climate (Igomu and Idoga, 2017). Makurdi has tropical climate conditions with distinct wet and dry seasons. The dry season starts from November to March while rainy season starts from April and end in October. In the past, Benue state experiences a bimodal rainfall distribution pattern with one peak in July and another in September. Recent meteorological data point to unimodal pattern with the single peak in August. The mean annual rainfall for Benue state varies between 1000 and 1600 mm. The mean minimum air temperature of Makurdi is 16.20 °C to 17.20 °C during the period of harmattan, which is December to February. The mean maximum air temperature is 37.7 °C in March prior to the onset of rains. The slope of the area is 0 to 5 % and the mean elevation above mean sea level is about 93 m (Ojanuga and Ekwoanya, 1995).

Field studies

Field studies involved taking soil samples using a core sampler as well as the collection of bulk soil samples for laboratory analysis. Soil samples were collected using grid method with a core sampler based on the nature of the slope of the study plot of 600 X 400 meters. Five samples were collected to form composite samples from each of the upper crest location, the mid slope and foot (lower) slope, respectively to enhance proper study of the soil of the areas. The soil samples were described using the pattern outlined in the Soil Survey Manual (2010).

Laboratory analyses

Standard laboratory procedures were employed in the investigation of the physical and chemical characteristic of the soil samples collected from the field. The bulk soil samples collected from the field were air dried. The air-dried samples were gently crushed using mortar and pestle. The samples were sieved through 2 mm and 0.5 mm sieves and used for laboratory analyses. For laboratory analyses like particle size distribution, Boyoucos hygrometer method was used. Electrometric method as described by Hesse (1971) was used for pH analysis. Walkley-Black method as described by Hesse (1971) was used for organic determination. Total nitrogen was determined by the use of macro Kjeldahl method

Land evaluation procedures

The conventional parametric method was used for the suitability evaluation of the land (FAO 1976), where soils were placed in suitability classes by matching their characteristics with the established requirements for groundnut (Table 1). The aggregate suitability class indicates the most limiting characteristics of the land. The parameters used for the land quality calculation include rainfall, mean annual temperature, slope, wetness, drainage. While those of soil characteristics included texture, coarse fragment, soil pH. Other fertility indicators were base saturation, organic carbon and available phosphorus.

SOURCE: MINISTRY OF LANDS AND SURVEYING, MAKURDI, BENUE STATE.

Figure 2. Map of Makurdi Local Government area of Benue State.

Table 1. Soil and Climatic Requirement for Suitability of Groundnut (*Aracis hypogaea*)

Land characteristics	Rate	100-95	84-40	39-20	19-0
	Class	S1	S2	S3	N1
Climatic ©					
Annual rainfall	Mm	600-1500	500-1250	450-850	-
Mean Annual Max Temp.	°C	30-35	15-20	21-30	-
Relative humidity	%	50-80	>80	-	-
Length of dry season	Days	120-150	110-130	90-130	-
Topography (t)					
Slope					
	%	0-2	8-Apr	16-Aug	>30-50
Wetness	%	0-4	16-Aug	16-30	>30
Flooding	Class	FO	FI	Aeric	Poor
Drainage	Class	Good	Poor	Poor	Drainage
Soil physical properties (s)					
Texture/structure					
	Class	LS,S	SL,S	LS, S	S
Coarse fragment (0-50cm)	%	<3	15-35	35-50	-
Fertility (f)					
CEC	(cmol/ kg) clay	>24	<16(-)	<16(+)	-
Base saturation	%	>50	20-35	<20	-
pH	Water	5.9-7.0	5.5-8.0	5.0-8.0	-
Organic carbon (OM)	(0-50) %	>2	0.8-12	<0.8	-
Available P	mg/kg	>22	13-Jul	7-Mar	<3
Extractable K	cmol/kg	>0.50	0.20-0.30	0.10-0.20	<0.10
Total Nitrogen	%	>0.15	0.08-0.10	0.04-0.06	<0.08

Key: FO-No Flooding, FI- Seasonal Flooding, FR-Flooding Rare, C-Clay, CL- Clay Loam, LS- Loamy Sand, SL- Sandy Loam, LCS- Loamy Clay Sand, CS- Clay Sand, S- Sand, S1- Highly suitable, S2- Moderately suitable, S3-Marginally suitable, N1- Currently not suitable.

SOURCE: Adesemuyi (2014).

Results and Discussions

The particle size distribution values for the soil mapping units are shown in Table 2. The values revealed the sandy nature of all the soil units. Soils of units I and III generally have loamy sand surface texture while, soil unit II had sandy loam surface texture. The sand fraction of the three soil units ranged from 70.64 to 71.08 %. This high fraction of sand could be attributed to the nature of the parent material (sandstone). Sand fraction decreased with depth in all soil units. The clay content of the soils was moderate to high ranging from 14.92 to 16.20 %, while silt fraction ranged from 13.0 to 14.0 %. Because of illuviation, the clay content of the soils was higher in the mid crest than the top crest. The weak fine to medium crumbs of upper crest of all soil units (Table 2) could be attributed to their low level of organic matter and sandy nature of the soils. In the entire field, the three units had moderate to strong, medium to coarse sub-angular blocky structures. This may be attributed to the corresponding increase in clay content in the sub soils.

The pH (H₂O) of the soils ranged between 6.10 and 6.16 (Table 2) indicating strong to slightly acid (USDA, 2010). There was a general tendency among these soils to have higher pH values at surface, which may decreased with depth. Ojanuga and Ekwoanya (1995) attributed the slightly higher pH in the upper most soil horizon to the accumulation of exchangeable calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) derived from plant roots and litter decomposition, as well as biogenetic cycling of bases. The pH values of the soil units I and III were higher than those of Unit II. As the cations are leached, hydrogen ion (H⁺) from water (H₂O) replaces the leached cations in the exchange complex to balance the charge. Soil acidity is known to affect most soil nutrients especially P, N, S, and micronutrients (Agbede, 2009).

The organic carbon (Table 2) was low according to the ratings of Esu (1991) with values ranging from 0.59 to 0.64 %. These values may decreased with depth in all the three Soil Units due to the concentration of plant roots and residue on the soils. The low organic carbon content of these soil units could be attributed to annual bush burning in the area as well as the native vegetation cover and climate. According to Igomu and Idoga, (2017), drainage appeared to have strong influence on the organic carbon content of the soil. Earthworms and other organic fauna increase organic carbon content of the soil by breaking and biochemically altering fresh organic matter through mixing with inorganic materials and later excreting them to form a moist homogenous blend of the organic and mineral matters, which prevents rapid loss of humic compounds (Esu, 1982). More earthworm casts were seen on the surface of soil unit II than units I. Total nitrogen values ranged from 0.13 to 0.18 % for all the soil units studied. The distribution of total nitrogen follows the same pattern as organic carbon in topo sequence. Osujieke et al. (2018) revealed that savannah soils are generally low in total nitrogen. This is due to the low organic carbon content of the soils of the savannah agro-ecological zone. It is obvious that climate, vegetation and human activities contribute to the low level of nitrogen. The available phosphorus of the soil had values ranging from 2.8 to 3.2 mg/kg and were generally low when compared with the ratings of Chude et al. (2011). The surface values of the amount of available phosphorus, which may decreased with soil depth shows that much of the available P is in organic forms associated with organic matter.

The values of Ca^{2+} , K^+ and Na^+ were low while Mg^{2+} was moderate when compared with the ratings of Landon (1991) in all the soil units. The low values of exchangeable bases of these soils maybe due to intensity of weathering and lateral translocation of bases. The amount of exchangeable calcium (Ca) ranged between 2.5 and 3.0 cmol (+)/kg of soil. Magnesium (Mg) ranged between 2.3 and 2.7 cmol (+)/kg of soil. Potassium (K) ranged between 0.24 and 0.27 cmol (+)/kg of soil while Sodium (Na) ranged between 0.21 and 0.24 cmol (+)/kg of soil. The predominance of Ca over the other cations in these soils may be because of all the exchangeable cations, Ca is least easily lost from the soil environment (Brady, 1974). The CEC of the soil ranged from 6.37 to 7.31 cmol/kg of soil. The lowest CEC values were recorded in unit III owing to their low organic carbon content and perhaps low clay content. Donahue et al., (1976) reported that some sandy soils of the tropics with dominant clay might have low CEC hence, low fertility. Base saturation by sum of cations ranged between 82.42 and 85.51 % which is rated very high (Idoga and Ibrahim, 2012). The high base status showed that the soils had high native fertility, which is confirmed by the luxuriant growth of the vegetation of the soil.

Land Suitability Evaluation

The overall methodology followed involved the selection of attributes relevant to groundnut production, generation of data layers, weighting and overlaying of the data layers to generate a land suitability map for groundnut production. Elevation dataset was used as proxy for climatic variables (rainfall and temperature) and it was generated by reclassifying the digital elevation model (DEM). The distance dataset representing accessibility was generated using the Euclidean distance tool. Each data layer was reclassified into suitability classes based on groundnut requirement. The suitability levels assigned to each dataset were defined based on literature, expert knowledge, observation and practical experiences. The suitability levels were ranked as highly suitable, moderately suitable, marginally suitable, currently not suitable and permanently not suitable based on the suitability classification structure (Adesemuyi, 2014). The datasets generated were finally combined using the weighted sum overlay to generate the land suitability map for rainfed groundnut production. The matching of land characteristics used for suitability ratings of sites for groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*.) production in Makurdi (Table 3) with land and soil requirements for suitability rating of groundnut (Table 1) resulted in the suitability classes of the soil mapping units as shown in Fig. 3. The region was optimal or near optimal in mean annual temperature, relative humidity, length of dry season, slope and base saturation.

Textural classes of the COATRF I soils ranged from loamy sand to sandy loam, thus, considered moderately suitable (S2s) for the cultivation of groundnut. The soil texture for optimum groundnut performance is sandy loam or loam (Sys, 1985). However, topography and low soil fertility levels limited the soils into the moderately suitable (S2tf) subclass for groundnut production. Based on these assessments, none of the soils was considered highly suitable for groundnut cultivation in the area. Soils of COATRF I and II were classified into moderately suitable (S2f) subclass as a result of their low nutrients status

Table 2. Physical and chemical characteristics of the soils

S/NO	Sample Identity	Sand %	Clay %	Silt %	pH H ₂ O	OC %	Av.P mg/kg	N %	K	Na	Mg (cmol/kg)	Ca	CEC
1	Upper crest	70.8	16.2	13	6.12	1	3.2	0.18	0.27	0.24	2.7	3	7.31
2	Mid slope	71.08	14.92	14	6.16	1	2.8	0.13	0.24	0.21	2.3	2.5	6.37
3	Foot slope	70.64	16	13.36	6.1	1	3.1	0.15	0.26	0.24	2.6	2.8	6.9

OC= organic carbon, Av.P= available phosphorus, CEC= cation exchange capacity, BS= base saturation

Table 3. Land characteristics used for suitability rating of sites for groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) production in Makurdi

Land characteristics	Unit	COATRF 1	COATRF 2	COATRF 3
Climatic ©				
Annual Rainfall	mm	1000-1600	1000-1600	1000-1600
Mean Annual Max. Temp.	°C	37.7	37.7	37.7
Relative Humidity	%	>80	>80	>80
Length of Dry Season	Days	120-150	120-150	120-150
Topography (t)				
Slope	%	0-5	0-4	0-4
Wetness (w)				
Flooding	Class	FO	FR	FI
Drainage	Class	WD	WD	ID
Soil Physical Properties (s)				
Texture/Structure	Class	95	90	80
Coarse fragments(0.50cm)	%	<3	15-35	35-55
Fertility (f)				
CEC	(cmol*kg ⁻¹)	7.94	8.03	10.48
Base Saturation	%	93	82	79
PH	Water	5.5-7.0	5.5-8.0	5.0-8.0
Organic matter (OM)	-0.50%	1.27	1.09	1.21
Avail. P	cmol*kg ⁻¹	3.64	3.07	3.26
Extractable K	cmol*kg ⁻¹	0.25	0.27	0.29
Total Nitrogen	%	0.078	0.069	0.074
COATRF- College of Agronomy Teaching and Research Farm.				
FO- No Flooding, FI- Seasonal Flooding, FR- Flooding Rare, WD- Well Drained, WI- Poorly Drained.				

Table 4. Land characteristics used for suitability ratings of sites for groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea L.*) production

Land Characteristic	COATRF 1	COATRF 2	COATRF 3
CLIMATE ©			
Annual Rainfall	100=S1	100=S1	100=S1
Mean Annual Max. Temp.	100=S1	100=S1	100=S1
Relative Humidity	100=S1	100=S1	100=S1
Length of Dry Season	100=S1	100=S1	100=S1
Topography (t)			
Slope	80=S2	84=S2	95=S1
Wetness (W)			
Flooding	100=S1	85=S2	71=S3
Drainage	95=S1	75=S2	65=S3
Soil Physical Properties			
(s)	95=S1	90=S2	80=S3
Texture/Structure			
Coarse Fragment (0-50cm)	90=S2	90=S2	90=S2
Fertility (f)			
CEC	65=S3	69=S3	71=S3
Base Saturation	90=S1	82=S1	79=S1
PH	90=S1	80=S2	38=S3
Organic carbon (OC)	84=S2	75=S2	80=S2
Avail. P	65=S3	70=S3	15=S3
Extractable K	75=S2	80=S2	54=S3
Aggregate Suitability	S1tf	S2tf	S3wf
Class			

KEY: COATRF-Collage of Agronomy Teaching and Research Farm, S1- Highly suitable, S2- Moderately suitable, S3- Marginally Suitable

Figure 3. Suitability map for groundnut production in COATRF Makurdi

Table 5. Metrological data of mean values of maximum and minimum temperature in degree celsius, relative humidity and total amount of rainfall in millimetres (mm) in Makurdi

CLIMATIC DATA FOR BENUE STATE														
Month	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	T	M
2015	38.80	36.30	35.80	36.90	35.00	32.70	30.90	30.90	30.90	32.40	34.00	33.70		
2016	35.40	38.40	35.70	34.00	33.40	31.80	30.90	30.60	30.90	32.50	35.30	35.40		
2017	36.40	38.10	39.50	36.30	33.20	32.10	31.00	30.10	31.10	34.60	36.00	35.60		
Max	36.80	37.80	37.00	35.00	33.80	32.20	30.90	30.50	30.90	33.20	35.10	34.90	408.60	34.00
Min	17.90	23.80	24.20	24.20	24.00	24.40	23.60	23.00	23.50	23.30	23.80	17.50		
2016	21.70	26.00	25.30	24.10	23.60	23.20	23.50	23.10	23.30	22.40	23.40	23.40		
2017	20.30	20.30	26.80	25.70	24.50	23.80	22.50	22.90	23.70	22.60	22.90	18.20		
M	19.90	23.40	25.40	24.70	24.00	24.00	23.20	23.00	23.50	22.70	23.40	19.70	276.90	23.00
2015	40.00	71.00	70.00	65.00	72.00	76.00	82.00	85.00	85.00	79.00	69.00	27.00		
2016	27.00	29.00	73.00	73.00	79.00	80.00	84.00	87.00	84.00	85.00	81.00	52.00		
2017	49.00	31.00	59.00	70.00	78.00	80.00	84.00	86.00	82.00	88.00	69.00	51.00		
M	38.70	43.70	67.30	69.30	76.30	78.70	83.30	86.60	83.70	84.40	79.30	43.30	833.60	69.50
2015	23.00	41.00	43.00	39.00	53.00	50.00	68.00	71.00	69.00	66.00	66.00	19.00		
2016	15.00	20.00	52.00	57.00	57.00	66.00	66.00	70.00	72.00	72.00	65.00	26.00		
2017	24.00	11.00	31.00	47.00	63.00	68.00	70.00	74.00	70.00	76.00	40.00	31.00		
M	20.70	24.00	42.00	47.70	57.70	61.30	68.00	71.70	70.30	71.30	57.00	25.30	617.00	51.50
Month	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	T	M
Rainfall (mm)	00.00	118.80	3.90	17.70	37.20	123.60	139.70	339.10	127.30	82.90	16.80	00.00	1007.00	
2015	00.00	00.00	47.60	91.10	238.00	49.40	215.60	213.80	268.90	116.10	00.00	00.00	1240.50	
2016	00.00	00.00	00.00	86.30	245.80	123.90	95.70	224.30	158.70	73.90	0.60	00.00	1009.20	
2017	00.00	00.00	17.20	65.10	173.70	98.90	150.30	259.1	184.90	90.90	5.80	0.00	1085.57	
M	0.00	39.60												

Key: Temp. = Temperature; RH = Relative humidity, M = mean

Conclusions

This research offered some valuable insight with outcomes vital to groundnut production in Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi, Benue State of Nigeria. The suitability assessment results showed that although, certain qualities or characteristics such as mean annual temperature, relative humidity and base saturation were optimum for groundnut cultivation, there was however, no highly suitable (S1) land for groundnut cultivation in the area. Soils of COATRF I and II was classified into marginally suitable (S2f) subclass, due to their low nutrients' levels. COATRF I and II Units of the area were moderately suitable (S2tf) due to topography and low soil fertility. It can further be concluded that the generated land suitability map with overall classification accuracy which was 320 meters of the farm land can rightly be used as a guide in decision making for groundnut production. Therefore, it is conclusive that the soils of College of Agronomy Research Farm Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi, is moderately suitable for groundnut production.

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